

Study 1: Air Quality Recovery

Start of Block: Consent Form

ConsentForm Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! You must be 18 years or older to participate. We are investigating how people think about current events. In this study, you will first be asked to read a news article about a current event. You will then be asked questions about a current event. The article you read and the issue you answer questions about may or may not be related, depending on which conditions you get randomly assigned to. The study will take 10 minutes or less. You will receive \$2.00 for your participation. There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]. [REDACTED] Should you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, please contact the Oberlin College Institutional Review Board, ([REDACTED]). Thank you!

Consent Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study.

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and consent to participate (1)
- No I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study. = No I do not consent

Page Break

issue_importance How important do you think each of the following issues is in the United States today?

	Not important (1)	Somewhat important (2)	Very important (3)	Extremely important (4)
Healthcare (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Terrorism and national security (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
COVID-19 (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gun policy (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Consent Form

Start of Block: Experimental Condition

ExpLink You have been assigned to read an article about *COVID-19*. Please click on [this link](#) (or cut and paste the link below into your browser), which will take you to a new tab. Clicking on this link will NOT close you out of the experiment. Please read the article, then return to this tab to finish the survey.

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1DhbHkN9uZZjXjLG4Htod1UbHG9MhAK_DQkFnzSlliBk/e/dit?usp=sharing

ExpTimer Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Experimental Condition

Start of Block: Control Condition

ControlLink You have been assigned to read an article about *travel*. Please click on [this link](#) (or cut and paste the link below into your browser), which will take you to a new tab. Clicking on this link will NOT close you out of the experiment. Please read the article, then return to this tab to finish the survey.

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1VWK5r-K4q30pItVA26X5TymOI3-6VtCpaz4ovyAJbDk/edit?usp=sharing>

ControlTimer Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: Control Condition

Start of Block: Dependent Variables

Q21 In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

WARMER From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
 - I'm not sure (3)
 - No, it has not (2)
-

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... = Yes, it has

Or From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... = I'm not sure

WHYWARMER Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
- Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
- I'm not sure (6)

Page Break

severity How likely is it that climate change is happening or will happen?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Between low and moderate chance (4)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - Between moderate and high chance (6)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

p_vulnerability How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Between small and moderate impact (4)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Between moderate and large impact (6)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

c_vulnerability How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
- Very small impact (2)
- Small impact (3)
- Between small and moderate impact (4)
- Moderate impact (5)
- Between moderate and large impact (6)
- Large impact (7)
- Very large impact (8)

Page Break

P_GWRISK How much risk do you believe climate change poses to YOUR health, safety, or prosperity?

- No risk at all (1)
 - Very low risk (2)
 - Low risk (3)
 - Between low and moderate risk (4)
 - Moderate risk (5)
 - Between moderate and high risk (6)
 - High risk (7)
 - Very high risk (8)
-

C_GWRISK Overall, how much risk do you believe climate change poses to human health, safety, or prosperity?

- No risk at all (1)
 - Very low risk (2)
 - Low risk (3)
 - Between low and moderate risk (4)
 - Moderate risk (5)
 - Between moderate and high risk (6)
 - High risk (7)
 - Very high risk (8)
-

Page Break

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

P_per_efficacy How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
- Moderately hard (2)
- Slightly hard (3)
- Slightly easy (4)
- Moderately easy (5)
- Extremely easy (6)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

P_res_efficacy How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
- Moderately ineffective (2)
- Slightly ineffective (3)
- Slightly effective (4)
- Moderately effective (5)
- Extremely effective (6)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

C_per_efficacy How **easy or hard** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
- Moderately hard (2)
- Slightly hard (3)
- Slightly easy (4)
- Moderately easy (5)
- Extremely easy (6)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

C_res_efficacy How **effective** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
- Moderately ineffective (2)
- Slightly ineffective (3)
- Slightly effective (4)
- Moderately effective (5)
- Extremely effective (6)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

G_per_efficiency How **easy or hard** would it be for the United States government to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
- Moderately hard (2)
- Slightly hard (3)
- Slightly easy (4)
- Moderately easy (5)
- Extremely easy (6)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

G_res_efficiency How **effective** would it be for the United States government to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
- Moderately ineffective (2)
- Slightly ineffective (3)
- Slightly effective (4)
- Moderately effective (5)
- Extremely effective (6)

protection_motivatio How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- on climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
 - Moderately unlikely (2)
 - Slightly unlikely (3)
 - Slightly likely (4)
 - Moderately likely (5)
 - Extremely likely (6)
-

pers_behavior How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Reduce your annual air travel (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce your household energy use (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase your use of walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase carbon offsets (donate money for projects that reduce the release of CO2) (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Optimism How likely is it that human beings will effectively respond to climate change?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
- Moderately unlikely (2)
- Slightly unlikely (3)
- Slightly likely (4)
- Moderately likely (5)
- Extremely likely (6)

End of Block: Dependent Variables

Start of Block: Demographics

ethnicity How do you identify? (Check all that apply.)

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
 - Asian (4)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
 - Hispanic (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

gender What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - I identify as (3) _____
-

age What is your year of birth?

education What is the highest level degree or level of education you have completed?

▼ No schooling (1) ... Doctorate (14)

pol_affiliation What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat (1)
 - Independent (2)
 - Republican (3)
 - Other (4) _____
-

pol_leaning Would you describe yourself as relatively more conservative, liberal, or right in the middle?

- Extremely liberal (1)
- Liberal (2)
- Slightly liberal (3)
- Moderate, middle of the road (4)
- Slightly conservative (5)
- Conservative (6)
- Extremely conservative (7)

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Questions about article

attentioncheck The article I read was about

- Air quality in India (1)
- Historical landmarks in India (2)
- I did not read an article (3)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If The article I read was about = Air quality in India

Or The article I read was about = Historical landmarks in India

article_eval Think about the article you read earlier. I thought the article was...

	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly agree (7)
Boring (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Depressing (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Uplifting (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interesting (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Easy to understand (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Confusing (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Questions about article

Start of Block: Block 6

debrief Thank you for your participation in this study! We are exploring how stories about COVID-19 impact people's thoughts and feelings about climate change. Some of you read an article about how the air quality in India dramatically improved during the shut-down. Others of you read an article about traveling in India. We hypothesize that seeing how quickly natural systems recover when humans change their behavior may make people more hopeful about solving climate change.

Your study completion code is TULSA232.

open_feedback This is our very first study on this topic. If you have any thoughts to share related to our hypothesis, or suggestions for how we could improve this survey, we would be very grateful to hear them.

End of Block: Block 6

Study 2: Prospection 1

Start of Block: Consent Form

Q128 Welcome!

Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! This survey is part of a larger research project conducted at Oberlin College. We are interested in getting feedback on one writing prompt. This study will take approximately 28 minutes. To thank you for your time, you will receive \$4.50. There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] For questions concerning the rights of human subjects, please contact [REDACTED]

- I am 18 years or older (1)
- I am not 18 years or older (2)

Q142 By checking below, you acknowledge that you have read the above information and give your consent to participate in our study and consent for us to analyze the resulting data. The data will be used for an honors thesis and potentially for conference presentations.

- I consent, begin the study (1)
- I do not consent (2)

End of Block: Consent Form

Start of Block: STS

Q41 For each of the statements below, please indicate whether or not the statement is characteristic of you or of what you believe.

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neither Agree nor Disagree (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)
The Earth, including all its inhabitants, is a living system. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All the Earth's systems, from the climate to the economy, are interconnected. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Seemingly small choices we make today can ultimately have major consequences. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Individual people are not as separate from one another as they seem. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Environmental problems, social problems, and economic problems are all separate issues. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
When I have to make a decision in my life, I tend to see all kinds of possible consequences to each choice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

(6)

I learn best when I can see how the different pieces of a subject relate to one another. (7)

I like to know how events or information fit into the big picture. (8)

Ultimately, we can break all problems down into what is simply right or wrong (9)

Rules and laws should not change a lot over time. (10)

Everything is constantly changing. (11)

Only very large events can significantly change big systems like economies or ecosystems. (12)

Adding just one more small farm upstream from a lake can permanently alter that lake. (13)

My health has nothing to do with what is happening in

the real world.
(14)

It is possible
for a
community to
organize into a
new form that
was not
planned or
designed by an
authority or
government.
(15)

End of Block: STS

Start of Block: Present

Q178 Our country is at a crossroads with economic and ecological disaster. Decisions we make today may degrade pristine natural areas, increase food prices, and delay the availability of clean energy. It may be difficult to see how our individual choices affect the whole. Things that seem to be in our best interest actually threaten our well-being and financial prosperity in the not-so-long term. However, we are adaptable. We may be able to avoid an era of economic and ecological misery.

Please think about your neighborhood, given the prominent issues of our time. Think about its typical weather, its relative wealth, and its various areas. What do you see? What do you hear? What do you smell? Please describe. (4-6 sentences)

Q179 Who is there? What are they doing? (3-5 sentences)

Q180 How are things changing? (2-4 sentences)

End of Block: Present

Start of Block: Negative

Q175 In the early 1900s, American pioneers struck west in large numbers and settled down to farm. With new mechanized farming techniques, more than five million acres of prairie were plowed for agricultural use. Although the new land and technology were supposed to bring prosperity to Americans, the wheat crops did not maintain the topsoil in the same way as natural grasses. When drought struck, this fertile dirt blew away in massive black blizzards, leaving the land inhospitable. The resulting disaster, called the Dust Bowl, caused millions of Americans to flee the region in poverty, and worsened the Great Depression, one of the bleakest eras of the country's history.

Once again, our country is at a crossroads with economic and ecological disaster. Decisions we make today are threatening the well-being of citizens in the decades to come. If continued, they will also degrade pristine natural areas, increase food prices, and delay the availability of clean energy. As with the Dust Bowl, it may be difficult to see how our individual choices affect the whole. Things that seem to be in our best interest actually threaten our well-being and financial prosperity in the not-so-long term. However, we are adaptable. We may be able to avoid a similar era of economic and ecological misery.

Please visualize your neighborhood 30 years in the future. The prominent issues of our time have continued and worsened, so temperatures have risen, the neighborhood is poorer, American landscapes are littered with trash, and you are dependent on increasingly expensive fuels for energy. What do you see? What do you hear? What do you smell? Please describe. (4-6 sentences)

Q176 Who is there? What are they doing? (3-5 sentences)

Q177 What happened in between now and then that could have led to this outcome? (2-4 sentences)

End of Block: Negative

Start of Block: Positive

Q169 In the early 1900s, American pioneers struck west in large numbers and settled down to farm. With new mechanized farming techniques, more than five million acres of prairie were plowed for agricultural use. Although the new land and technology were supposed to bring prosperity to Americans, the wheat crops did not maintain the topsoil in the same way as natural grasses. When drought struck, this fertile dirt blew away in massive black blizzards, leaving the land inhospitable. The resulting disaster, called the Dust Bowl, caused millions of Americans to

flee the region in poverty, and worsened the Great Depression, one of the bleakest eras of the country's history.

Once again, our country is at a crossroads with economic and ecological disaster. Decisions we make today are threatening the financial well-being of citizens in the decades to come. If continued, they will also degrade pristine natural areas, increase food prices, and delay the availability of clean energy. As with the Dust Bowl, it may be difficult to see how our individual choices affect the whole. Things that seem to be in our economic interest actually threaten our well-being and financial prosperity in the not-so-long term. However, we are adaptable. We may be able to avoid a similar era of economic loss and misery.

Please visualize your neighborhood 30 years in the future. The prominent issues of our time have been fixed, so temperatures have stabilized, the neighborhood is richer, American landscapes are protected, and you are self-reliant for energy from solar panels and other renewables. What do you see? What do you hear? What do you smell? Please describe. (4-6 sentences)

Q170 Who is there? What are they doing? (3-5 sentences)

Q171 What happened in between now and then that could have led to this outcome? (2-4 sentences)

End of Block: Positive

Start of Block: Mood

Mood Please rate your current mood.

I don't feel this way I very much feel this way
0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

End of Block: Mood

Start of Block: Systems_State

Systems_State Everyone has different opinions and experiences. We'd like to know how *you* see things. For each question below, click on the number that best represents your opinion.

	1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	5 (5)
My local actions affect things that happen at a global scale (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Things that happen on a global scale affect my local community (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Things that I do now affect things that happen later (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Things that have happened in the past continue to affect the present (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
It is important to consider how our current actions now affect future generations (5)	<input type="radio"/>				

End of Block: Systems_State

Start of Block: Climate Change

CC Politics To what extent do you agree with the following statement?

	Definitely No (1)	Probably No (2)	Maybe No; Maybe Yes (3)	Probably Yes (4)	Definitely Yes (5)
I believe that burning fossil fuels increases atmospheric temperature to some measurable degree. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A candidate's position on climate change is very important when deciding who to vote for (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We should subsidize renewable energy more than oil and natural gas (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Climate Change

Start of Block: How soon?

CC_Temporal When do you expect climate change to affect the following?

	Climate change won't affect this (1)	Not very soon, in several decades (2)	About a decade from now (3)	Soon, within a year or two (4)	It's already being affected (5)
The weather in my neighborhood (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The source of my electricity (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wildlife and landscapes in my area (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My relative wealth (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: How soon?

Start of Block: PEBT intro

Q216 For taking part in this survey, we will donate up to \$4.25 towards [Terrapass](#), a carbon offsets fund. This is in addition to your paid compensation.

A carbon offset is a reduction in emissions of carbon dioxide or greenhouse gases through funding projects in communities across the country that reduce greenhouse gas made in order to offset a GHG emissions made elsewhere. Carbon offsets are purchased to fund these projects and diminish the impact of your own GHG emissions, even though the projects are located elsewhere.

\$4.25 offsets about 1,000 pounds of CO², equivalent to 1/3 of the CO₂ emissions the average American makes in a month.

End of Block: PEBT intro

Start of Block: Instructions 1

Q215 In our computer task, you will have to choose a mode of transportation for a number of different trips.

After you have decided on a mode of transportation, you will have to wait until the trip is completed. When the trip is completed, you will have to choose a mode of transportation for the next trip.

You can choose between two newly developed transportation options, the '*sest*' and the '*dift*'.

In most cases, taking the *sest* will take more time than taking the *dift*. Depending on the nature of the trip, the travel time difference between the two options will be smaller or larger.

Also, taking the *dift* will consume some energy and produce CO² emissions. If you choose the *dift* option, a number of lights will be turned on for the duration of your trip. Each of these lights produces about half a pound of CO². This will lead to a deduction in your carbon offset fund equivalent to the CO² consumed during your trip, reducing the amount emission reductions you will make. The *sest*, on the other hand, is a zero-emissions mode of transportation.

Click next to see an example.

End of Block: Instructions 1

Start of Block: Example 1

Q217 In the example below, the participant chooses the *dift* option. As described earlier, choosing this option will turn on a number of lights and thus consume energy.

Click next to see how the lamps are turned on when the *dift* is chosen.

End of Block: Example 1

Start of Block: Example 2

Q219

Q220 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Example 2

Start of Block: Example 3

Q221 Since that was an example, nothing will be deducted from your carbon offsets.

Now you will start the task. There will be three separate blocks, each consisting of a series of trips. Between blocks, you can take a small break if you want.

Click next to begin with the first block.

End of Block: Example 3

Start of Block: Instructions large block

Q222 In this block, choosing the dift will consume a relatively large amount of energy.

If you choose the dift option, *12 out of 12* possible lights will be turned on. Powering these 12 lights produces about 6 pounds CO² and will lead to this being deducted from your carbon offsets -- in other words, *your choices will have a real environmental impact*.

If you choose the sest option, no lights will be turned on, no CO² will be produced, and no money will be deducted from your carbon offsets. However, for some trips, taking the sest will take longer than taking the dift.

For each trip, please choose whether you want to take the dift or the sest and then wait until the trip is completed.

End of Block: Instructions large block

Start of Block: Large choice 1

Q225

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 20 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 1

Start of Block: 12 on wait 5

Q498

Q499 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 12 on wait 5

Start of Block: 12 on wait 20

Q252

Q253 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 12 on wait 20

Start of Block: Large choice 2

Q226

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 2

Start of Block: None wait 25

Q262

Q263 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 25

Start of Block: Large choice 3

Q227

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 3

Start of Block: None wait 35

Q266

Q267 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 35

Start of Block: 12 on wait 10

Q248

Q249 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: 12 on wait 10

Start of Block: None wait 20

Q260

Q261 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 20

Start of Block: Large choice 4

Q231

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 4

Start of Block: Large choice 5

Q232

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 5

Start of Block: None wait 30

Q264

Q265 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 30

Start of Block: Large choice 6

Q233

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 6

Start of Block: 12 on wait 15

Q250

Q251 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 12 on wait 15

Start of Block: Large choice 7

Q237

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount

of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 7

Start of Block: Large choice 8

Q238

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 8

Start of Block: Large choice 9

Q239

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 45 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 9

Start of Block: None wait 45

Q270

Q271 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 45

Start of Block: Large choice 10

Q243

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 10

Start of Block: Large choice 11

Q244

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 11

Start of Block: None wait 40

Q268

Q269 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 40

Start of Block: Large choice 12

Q245

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 50 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 12 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a relatively large amount of energy (approx. 6 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

- SEST (1)
- DIFT (2)

End of Block: Large choice 12

Start of Block: None wait 50

Q272

Q273 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: None wait 50

Start of Block: Instructions medium block

Q274 In this block, choosing the dift will consume a medium amount of energy.

If you choose the dift option, *8 out of 12* possible lights will be turned on. Powering these 8 lights produces about 4 pounds of CO² and will lead to this being deducted from your carbon offsets.

If you choose the sest option, no lights will be turned on, no CO² will be produced, and no money will be deducted from your carbon offsets. However, for some trips, taking the sest will take longer than taking the dift. In other words, *your choices will have a real environmental impact*.

For each trip, please choose whether you want to take the dift or the sest and then wait until the trip is completed.

Click next to begin with the task.

End of Block: Instructions medium block

Start of Block: 8 on wait 5

Q299

Q300 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: 8 on wait 5

Start of Block: Med choice 1

Q278

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 20 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 1

Start of Block: Med choice 2

Q279

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 2

Start of Block: Med choice 3

Q280

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 3

Start of Block: 8 on wait 10

Q301

Q302 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: 8 on wait 10

Start of Block: Med choice 4

Q284

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

- SEST (1)
- DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 4

Start of Block: Med choice 5

Q285

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 5

Start of Block: Med choice 6

Q286

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 6

Start of Block: 8 on wait 15

Q303

Q304 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: 8 on wait 15

Start of Block: Med choice 7

Q290

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 7

Start of Block: Med choice 8

Q291

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 8

Start of Block: Med choice 9

Q292

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 45 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 9

Start of Block: 8 on wait 20

Q305

Q306 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: 8 on wait 20

Start of Block: Med choice 10

Q296

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 10

Start of Block: Med choice 11

Q297

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 11

Start of Block: Med choice 12

Q298

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 50 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 8 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a medium amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Med choice 12

Start of Block: Small instructions

Q307 In this block, choosing the dift will consume a small amount of energy.

If you choose the dift option, 4 out of 12 possible lights will be turned on. Powering these 4 lights produces about 4 pounds of CO² and will lead to this being deducted from your carbon offsets.

If you choose the sest option, no lights will be turned on, no CO² will be produced, and no money will be deducted from your carbon offsets. However, for some trips, taking the sest will take longer than taking the dift. In other words, *your choices will have a real environmental impact.*

For each trip, please choose whether you want to take the dift or the sest and then wait until the trip is completed.

Click next to begin with the task.

End of Block: Small instructions

Start of Block: 4 on wait 5

Q308

Q309 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 4 on wait 5

Start of Block: Sm choice 1

Q319

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 20 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 1

Start of Block: Sm choice 2

Q320

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 2

Start of Block: Sm choice 3

Q321

The next trip will take 5 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 3

Start of Block: 4 on wait 10

Q310

Q311 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 4 on wait 10

Start of Block: Sm choice 4

Q325

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 25 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 4

Start of Block: Sm choice 5

Q326

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 5

Start of Block: Sm choice 6

Q327

The next trip will take 10 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 6

Start of Block: 4 on wait 15

Q312

Q313 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 4 on wait 15

Start of Block: Sm choice 7

Q331

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 30 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 7

Start of Block: Sm choice 8

Q332

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 8

Start of Block: Sm choice 9

Q333

The next trip will take 15 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 45 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 9

Start of Block: 4 on wait 20

Q314

Q315 Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

End of Block: 4 on wait 20

Start of Block: Sm choice 10

Q337

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 35 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 15 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 10

Start of Block: Sm choice 11

Q338

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 40 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 20 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 11

Start of Block: Sm choice 12

Q339

The next trip will take 20 seconds by dift.

Taking the sest will take 50 seconds and will thus increase your travel time by 30 second(s).

Taking the dift will turn on 4 of 12 possible lights and will thus waste a small amount of energy (approx. 4 pounds of CO²) and reduce your carbon offset fund by such.

Which mode of transportation do you choose?

SEST (1)

DIFT (2)

End of Block: Sm choice 12

Start of Block: End of game

Q350 You have completed the last block.

Press next to continue to the survey questions.

End of Block: End of game

Start of Block: Demographics

Q344 Please describe your ethnicity. (Check all that apply).

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaskan Native (3)
 - Hispanic or Latino (4)
 - Asian (5)
 - Middle Eastern/North African (6)
 - Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander (7)
 - Other (please specify) (8)
-

Q345 What is your gender?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Other (3)

Q347 Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Republican, a Democrat, an Independent, or something else?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Independent (3)
- Other (4)

Q330 Here is a 7-point scale on which the political views that people might hold are arranged from extremely liberal (left) to extremely conservative (right). Where would you place yourself on this scale?

Extremely Liberal (0)	Extremely Liberal (0)	Liberal (1)	Slightly Liberal (2)	Neutral (3)	Slightly Conservative (4)	Conservative (5)	Extremely Conservative (6)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Q328 Thank you for taking part in our study. Your secret code is: FG42FG42MP4

The purpose of this study is to test whether certain writing exercises increase pro-environmental behavior through increasing systems thinking. Systems thinking is a way of conceptualizing reality and making decisions that emphasizes relationships and interdependencies. The writing prompt varied by participants. Some of you wrote about apocalypse and some of you wrote about utopia. Some of you wrote about the present, instead. Some wrote about nothing, as a control condition. We hypothesized that people who wrote about a positive future would be most likely to engage in pro-environmental behavior. If you have any questions or comments feel free to contact us at jcato@oberlin.edu

End of Block: Demographics

Study 3: Racial Disparity 1

Start of Block: Consent Form

ConsentForm Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! You must be 18 years or older to participate. We are investigating how people think about current events. In this study you will answer some questions about yourself, read a brief news article, and complete several short measures of how you think about the current issue you read about. The study will take 20 minutes or less. You will be compensated the amount you agreed upon before you entered into the survey. The news article you are assigned to read may be about a negative topic. There are no other known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED] [REDACTED] Should you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, please contact the Oberlin College Institutional Review Board, [REDACTED] Thank you!

consent Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study.

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and consent to participate (1)
- No, I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Block If Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study. = No, I do not consent

Page Break

Start of Block: Demographic Questions

ethnicity How do you identify? (Check all that apply)

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
 - Asian (4)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
 - Hispanic or Latino (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

gender What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - I identify as (3) _____
-

birth_year What is your year of birth?

pol_affiliation What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat (1)
 - Independent (2)
 - Republican (3)
 - Other (4) _____
-

pol_leaning Would you describe yourself as relatively conservative, liberal, or right in the middle?

- Extremely liberal (1)
 - Liberal (2)
 - Slightly liberal (3)
 - Moderate (4)
 - Slightly conservative (5)
 - Conservative (6)
 - Extremely conservative (7)
-

SES What is your wealth class? If you are unsure, you can use ["step one" of the income calculator](#) here:

<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2020/07/23/are-you-in-the-american-middle-class/>

- Upper income (1)
 - Middle income (2)
 - Lower income (3)
-

ZIP_code What is your postal code (also known as ZIP code)?

Page Break

news_sources Which sources do you receive news from multiple times a week? (Check all that apply)

- Television (1)
 - Radio (2)
 - News website or news app (3)
 - Print news sources (4)
 - Social media (5)
 - I do not receive news (6)
-

news_outlets Which news outlets do you use frequently? (Check all that apply)

- ABC News (1)
- BBC (2)
- Brietbart (3)
- Business Insider (4)
- BuzzFeed (5)
- CBS News (6)
- CNN (7)
- Daily Caller (8)
- Fox News (9)
- Guardian (10)
- Hill (11)
- HuffPost (12)
- MSNBC (13)
- NBC News (14)
- New York Post (15)
- New York Times (16)
- Newsweek (17)
- NPR (18)

- PBS (19)
- Politico (20)
- Sean Hannity Show (22)
- Time (23)
- Univision (24)
- USA Today (25)
- Vice (26)
- Vox (27)
- Wall Street Journal (28)
- Washington Examiner (29)
- Washington Post (30)
- None of the above (32)

Page Break

warmer From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
- I'm not sure (3)
- No, it has not (2)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the averag... = Yes, it has

Or From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the averag... = I'm not sure

why_warmer Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
- Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
- I'm not sure (6)

Page Break

pollution Have you experienced any of the following effects of pollution? (Check all that apply)

You've lived somewhere where...

- the water isn't safe to drink due to contamination (1)
 - the air isn't safe to breathe due to contamination (2)
 - the food isn't safe to eat due to contamination (3)
 - I have not experienced any of these effects (4)
-

climate_events Have you experienced any of the following climate events? (Check all that apply)

- Heat wave or heat stroke (1)
- Floods (6)
- Sea level rise (7)
- Hurricane (10)
- Wildfires (8)
- Drought (9)
- Animal extinction affecting your livelihood (4)
- Crop failure affecting your livelihood (5)
- I have not experienced any of these effects (11)

End of Block: Demographic Questions

Start of Block: Control Article

control You have been assigned to read an article about *climate change*. Please read the article carefully.

Hurricanes disproportionately harm small coastal communities

Communities on the coast already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from extreme weather disasters

By EMILY PONTECORVO

JUNE 7, 2020 10:59PM (UTC) When Hurricane Florence slammed into southeastern North Carolina in September 2018, the worst-hit communities were on the coast. Not to mention many were still in the process of rebuilding after Hurricane Matthew tore through two years earlier. According to Naeema Muhammad, organizing director of the North Carolina Environmental Justice Network, people in coastal towns like New Bern, Lumberton, and Faison, struggled to evacuate. "People are pretty much left on their own to try to navigate out of danger," Muhammad told Grist. When the flooding came, it flushed coal ash, animal waste, and human waste from wastewater treatment plants into the waterways, which spilled over riverbanks and into the streets. "People had to navigate through that water," she said. If you had been following coverage of the hurricane on one of the major nightly news shows at the time, you might have missed this story entirely. That's because not a single segment that aired on ABC's World News Tonight, the CBS Evening News, or the NBC Nightly News reported on the disparate impacts Florence had on smaller coastal communities, instead focusing on the impacts of the hurricane on larger cities affected, like Greenville, North Carolina. The media watchdog nonprofit analyzed 669 segments produced by those shows from 2017 to 2019 covering seven hurricanes, including Florence, and one tropical storm. Not one addressed the fact that these extreme weather events did not affect everyone in their paths equally — that the devastation they brought smaller coastal areas was far worse — despite ample research highlighting this disparity. "It does not come as a surprise at all," Muhammad said of the study. "We have a lot of issues going on in the floodplain areas that do not get addressed by the media." Small coastal communities already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from the extreme weather that becomes more common with climate change, especially hurricanes, flooding, and rising sea levels, because they tend to have less infrastructure than large cities. As the Media Matters report states, "These events expose vulnerabilities, but they often go unexplained — partly because broadcast TV news fails to even do the minimum of reporting on who is being harmed the most." Although extreme weather is projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at Berkeley University, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants.

control_time Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Control Article

Start of Block: Experimental Article

experimental You have been assigned to read an article about climate change. Please read the article carefully.

Hurricanes disproportionately harm communities of color
Communities of color already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from extreme weather disasters

By EMILY PONTECORVO

JUNE 7, 2020 10:59PM (UTC)

When Hurricane Florence slammed into southeastern North Carolina in September 2018, the worst-hit communities were already dealing with a litany of hazards: poverty, pollution from coal ash ponds and lagoons filled with livestock waste, and chemicals in the drinking water. Not to mention many were still in the process of rebuilding after Hurricane Matthew tore through two years earlier. According to Naeema Muhammad, organizing director of the North Carolina Environmental Justice Network, people in these largely black and brown communities in cities like New Bern and Lumberton, and rural towns like Faison, struggled to evacuate. "People are pretty much left on their own to try to navigate out of danger," Muhammad told Grist. When the flooding came, it flushed coal ash, animal waste, and human waste from wastewater treatment plants into the waterways, which spilled over riverbanks and into the streets. "People had to navigate through that water," she said. If you had been following coverage of the hurricane on one of the major nightly news shows at the time, you might have missed this story entirely. That's because not a single segment that aired on ABC's World News Tonight, the CBS Evening News, or the NBC Nightly News reported on the disparate impacts Florence had on marginalized communities, according to a new analysis by Media Matters. The media watchdog nonprofit analyzed 669 segments produced by those shows from 2017 to 2019 covering seven hurricanes, including Florence, and one tropical storm. Not one addressed the fact that these extreme weather events did not affect everyone in their paths equally — that the devastation they brought to poor communities and communities of color was far worse — despite ample research highlighting this disparity. "It does not come as a surprise at all," Muhammad said of the study. "We have a lot of issues going on in the floodplain areas that do

not get addressed by the media. It's mainly because of the faces in those areas," which are predominantly Black, Native American, and Latino. Marginalized communities already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from the extreme weather that becomes more common with climate change, from hurricanes and flooding to heat waves and wildfires. This is not just because they are more likely to live in the floodplain or the line of fire, although that is part of it, and is often the result of racist practices like redlining. Low-income and minority communities are also more likely to live in poor-quality housing and to not have the means to evacuate, rebuild, or relocate. As the Media Matters report states, "These events expose vulnerabilities stemming from historic and systemic inequities, but they too often go unexplained — partly because broadcast TV news fails to even do the minimum of reporting on who is being harmed the most." Although extreme weather is projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at Berkeley University, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants.

experimental_time Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Experimental Article

Start of Block: Questions about article

attentioncheck1 The article I read was about...

- The Ridgecrest Earthquakes (0)
- The Chico Wildfires (0)
- Hurricane Florence (1)
- New Mexico's Drought (0)
- I did not read an article (0)

Skip To: End of Block If The article I read was about... != Hurricane Florence

Display This Question:

If The article I read was about... = Hurricane Florence

attentioncheck2 The article I read said Hurricane Florence strongly impacted

- The fishing industry (0)
- Communities of color (2)
- Cruise ship routes (0)
- Small coastal towns (1)
- Beachside resorts (0)

affective_measures Think about the article you read earlier. The article made me feel...

	Strongly agree (1)	Agree (2)	Somewhat agree (3)	Somewhat disagree (5)	Disagree (6)	Strongly disagree (7)
Angry (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Guilty (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Overwhelmed (10)	<input type="radio"/>					
Indifferent (11)	<input type="radio"/>					
Afraid (12)	<input type="radio"/>					
Surprised (13)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hopeful (14)	<input type="radio"/>					
Calm (16)	<input type="radio"/>					
Motivated (18)	<input type="radio"/>					

End of Block: Questions about article

Start of Block: Enviro Questions

Q138 In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

vul_p How likely is it that the effects of climate change will impact you?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (4)
 - High chance (5)
 - Very high chance (6)
-

vul_c How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people in general?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (4)
 - High chance (5)
 - Very high chance (6)
-

vul_personal What is the likelihood of encountering the following events in your lifetime?

	No chance at all (1)	Very low chance (2)	Low chance (3)	Moderate chance (5)	High chance (7)	Very high chance (8)
Sea level rise (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hurricanes (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Wildfires (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Droughts (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Extreme heat waves (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

vul_collective What is the likelihood of encountering the following events for people in general?

	No chance at all (1)	Very low chance (2)	Low chance (3)	Moderate chance (5)	High chance (7)	Very high chance (8)
Sea level rise (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hurricanes (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Wildfires (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Droughts (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Extreme heat waves (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

severity_p How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

severity_c How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

PE_p How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

PE_c How **easy or hard** would it be for people in general to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_p How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_c How **effective** would it be for people in general to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

Page Break

Q46 In this section, we would like you to think about people who share the same ethnic identity you most strongly identify with.

vul_e How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people who share your ethnic identity?

- No chance (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

severity_e How much negative impact will climate change have on people who share your ethnic identity?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

PE_e How **easy or hard** would it be for people who share your ethnic identity to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_e How **effective** would it be for people who share your ethnic identity to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

Page Break

behavioral_motive How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- on climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
- Moderately unlikely (2)
- Slightly unlikely (3)
- Slightly likely (4)
- Moderately likely (5)
- Extremely likely (6)

Page Break

X→

behavioral_intent How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Minimize meat consumption (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support eco-friendly brands and businesses (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conserve household energy use (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Choose walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Join an organization that fights climate change (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Recycle
and/or
compost (10)

Support an
organization
that combats
environmental
racism (13)

Read or
watch news
related to
climate
change (14)

maladaptive_behavior How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Turn off the TV when it mentions climate disasters (hurricanes, wildfires, etc) (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Throw something recyclable in the trash to save time (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Avoid reading news articles with climate change in the title (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Drive somewhere within walking distance to save time (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

fear How afraid are you of the future?

- Extremely unafraid (1)
 - Moderately unafraid (2)
 - Slightly unafraid (3)
 - Slightly afraid (4)
 - Moderately afraid (5)
 - Extremely afraid (6)
-

optimism How optimistic are you for the future?

- Extremely pessimistic (1)
 - Moderately pessimistic (2)
 - Slightly pessimistic (3)
 - Slightly optimistic (4)
 - Moderately optimistic (5)
 - Extremely optimistic (6)
-

Page Break

End of Block: Enviro Questions

Start of Block: Self Affirmation task

self_affirmation Please take a moment to identify a value that is important to you. Briefly summarize this value below, and write a sentence or two about why this value is important to you. Describe a time when you expressed this value in your life.

End of Block: Self Affirmation task

Study 4: Scientist 1

Start of Block: Consent Form

ConsentForm Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! You must be 18 years or older to participate. We are investigating how people think about current events. In this study, you will first be asked to read a news article about a current event. You will then be asked questions about a current event. The article you read and the issue you answer questions about may or may not be related, depending on which conditions you get randomly assigned to. The study will take 10 minutes or less. You will receive \$1.75 for your participation. There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]. Should you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, please contact [REDACTED]. Thank you!

Consent Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study.

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and consent to participate (1)
- No I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study. = No I do not consent

End of Block: Consent Form

Start of Block: COVID Condition

ExpLink You have been assigned to read an article about *COVID scientists*.

Covid Article For Experts Who Study Coronaviruses, a Grim Vindication BY CHARLES SCHMIDT 06.08.2020

THE NOW PROPHETIC words could be found buried at the end of a research paper published in the journal *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* in October of 2007: “The presence of a large reservoir of SARS-CoV-like viruses in horseshoe bats, together with the culture of eating exotic animals in southern China, is a time bomb.” The warning – made 13 years ago – came after a wave of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) killed 744 people around the globe. It was among the first to predict the emergence of something like SARS-CoV-2, the virus behind the COVID-19 pandemic. 60% of infectious diseases that have never before reached humans originate in domesticated animals and wildlife. These are often bats, rodents, or non-human primates. Scientists estimate that there are as many as 800,000 zoonotic viruses that could infect humans. “Every future viral threat that people could get already exists and is circulating in those animals — always has been,” said Dennis Carroll, an expert on zoonotic diseases. He is also the former head of the emerging threats division of the United States Agency for International Development, or USAID. Within USAID, Carroll developed a virus catch-and-release project called PREDICT. The program included scientists and researchers from the University of California, Davis and EcoHealth Alliance — all with the goal of discovering new viruses before they spill over into people. Jonna Mazet, the organization’s global director, said that PREDICT collected 168,000 samples from people and animals, and identified more than 900 new viruses. Of those, 160 were coronaviruses — in the same family as SARS-CoV-2. To many experts, the coronavirus pandemic — and the United States’ inability to contain it — has felt like the climate crisis “at warp speed,” says ecologist Jeff Dukes. Both disasters were predicted by scientists and could have been prevented, or at least mitigated, by swift and early action. Climate change is also responsible for the rapid spread of zoonotic diseases, like COVID-19. Events like drought, flooding, and extreme weather force food production to breach habitats populated by virus-carrying wild animals. Although these events are projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at UC Berkeley, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants. Whether or not the pandemic ultimately helps or hinders the prospects for U.S. and global climate action, however, the two crises remain inextricably linked.

ExpTimer Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: COVID Condition

Start of Block: Climate Change Condition

ControlLink You have been assigned to read an article about *climate change scientists*.

CC Article 40 Years Ago, Scientists Predicted Climate Change BY NEVILLE
NICHOLLS 07.22.2019

THE PROPHETIC WORDS could be found in the conclusion of the Charney Report, created by 10 distinguished climate scientists after a meeting about carbon dioxide and climate change in 1979: “We estimate the most probable warming for a doubling of CO₂ to be near 3°C with a probable error of 1.5°C.” The Report – made over 40 years ago – was the first extensive evaluation of global climate change due to carbon dioxide. The scientists’ forecast of the global temperature rise proved to be incredibly accurate – they had predicted the planet’s warming to within a few hundredths of a degree. Earth-orbiting satellites and other technological advances have enabled scientists to collect data on a global scale. This data reveals the signals of a changing climate. As temperatures increase, the seas rise, droughts and wildfires grow worse, and extreme weather becomes more common. Eventually, entire regions become uninhabitable. “Scientific evidence for warming of the climate system is unequivocal,” said Myles Allen, the head of the Climate Dynamics group at Harvard University, and a scientist for the United States Environmental Protection Agency, or US EPA. Within the US EPA, Allen developed a project called PREDICT. The program included scientists and researchers from Harvard University and Climate Alliance – with the goal of creating climate models to forecast the planet’s temperature increases. Julie Cerqueira, the organization’s global director, said that PREDICT found that carbon dioxide levels today are higher than any point in the last 800,000 years. Temperature trends from around the world support these findings – every one of the past 40 years has been warmer than the 20th century average. To many experts, the coronavirus pandemic — and the United States’ inability to contain it — has felt like the climate crisis “at warp speed,” says ecologist Jeff Dukes. Both disasters were predicted by scientists and could have been prevented, or at least mitigated, by swift and early action. Climate change is also responsible for the rapid spread of zoonotic diseases, like COVID-19. Events like drought, flooding, and extreme weather force food production to breach habitats populated by virus-carrying wild animals. Although these events are projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at UC Berkeley, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants. Whether or not the pandemic ultimately helps or hinders the prospects for U.S. and global climate action, however, the two crises remain inextricably linked.

ControlTimer Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Climate Change Condition

Start of Block: Control Condition

Control Overview You have not been assigned to read an article. Please click the arrow to proceed.

End of Block: Control Condition

Start of Block: Attention Check

attentioncheck What is the purpose of the PREDICT project?

- Discovering new viruses before they spill over into people (1)
- Creating climate models to forecast the planet's temperature increases (2)
- Analyzing satellite data to predict the movement of comets (3)
- I did not read an article. (4)

Page Break

End of Block: Attention Check

Start of Block: Covid Belief Q's

Covid-threat How serious of a threat do you think COVID-19 poses as a global health crisis?

- Very serious threat (1)
 - No more serious than the common flu or cold virus (2)
 - Not serious at all (3)
-

face masks From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that wearing a facial mask significantly lowers the risk of COVID-19 transmission?

- Yes, wearing a mask is essential (1)
- Unsure, wearing a mask might help (2)
- No, wearing a mask is unnecessary (3)

End of Block: Covid Belief Q's

Start of Block: Climate Belief Q's

WARMER From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
 - I'm not sure (3)
 - No, it has not (2)
-

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

WHYWARMER Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
- Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
- I'm not sure (6)

End of Block: Climate Belief Q's

Start of Block: Dependent Variables

CC Overview In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

Page Break

p_severity How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact you?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

c_severity How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people in general?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

p_vulnerability How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

c_vulnerability How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

Page Break

X→

P_per_efficacy How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

X→

P_res_efficacy How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

Page Break

C_per_efficacy How **easy or hard** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

C_res_efficacy How **effective** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

Page Break

protection_motivatio How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- on climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
 - Moderately unlikely (2)
 - Slightly unlikely (3)
 - Slightly likely (4)
 - Moderately likely (5)
 - Extremely likely (6)
-

pers_behavior How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Eat a largely plant-based diet (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Keep your household energy use as low as possible (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase your use of walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase carbon offsets (donate money for projects that reduce the release of CO2) (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Optimism How likely is it that human beings will effectively respond to climate change?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
- Moderately unlikely (2)
- Slightly unlikely (3)
- Slightly likely (4)
- Moderately likely (5)
- Extremely likely (6)

End of Block: Dependent Variables

Start of Block: Scientist Questions

Climatologist Role How much do you agree with the following statements on climatologists?

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat Disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat Agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly Agree (7)
Climatologists should take an active role in public policy debates about scientific issues related to climate change (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists should focus on establishing sound scientific facts and stay out of public policy debates (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists' judgements are based solely on facts (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists act in accordance with public interest (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists are usually better at making good policy decisions about scientific issues related to climate change than	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

other people
(8)

Climatolog.Influence Please take a look at the following statements:

	None at all (1)	Not too much (2)	A fair amount (3)	A great deal (4)
How much confidence, if any, do you have in climatologists to act in the best interests of the public? (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As far as you know, how much are the federal government's policies on climate change influenced by evidence from scientists? (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As far as you know, how much are your state government's policies on climate change influenced by evidence from scientists? (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Scientist Questions

Start of Block: Demographics

ethnicity How do you identify? (Check all that apply.)

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
 - Asian (4)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
 - Hispanic (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

gender What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - I identify as (3) _____
-

age What is your year of birth?

education What is the highest level degree or level of education you have completed?

▼ No schooling (1) ... Doctorate (14)

pol_affiliation What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat (1)
 - Independent (2)
 - Republican (3)
 - Other (4) _____
-

pol_leaning Would you describe yourself as relatively more conservative, liberal, or right in the middle?

- Extremely liberal (1)
- Liberal (2)
- Slightly liberal (3)
- Moderate, middle of the road (4)
- Slightly conservative (5)
- Conservative (6)
- Extremely conservative (7)

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Closing

debrief Thank you for your participation in this study! We are exploring how information about scientists' accuracy in predicting issues of public concern (pandemics, climate crises, etc) impacts assessments of risk, and our willingness to take preventive action. Some of you read an article about the accuracy of epidemiologists' predictions. Others of you read an article about the accuracy of climate scientists' predictions. Still others read nothing at all. We hypothesize that reading about scientists' accurate predictions will increase concern about a pressing issue of our time (ie climate change), and therefore lead to people feeling more willing to take action

on behalf of climate change. We think it's possible that reading about epidemiologists' accuracy may be more psychologically impactful, as the effects of COVID-19 are much more immediate and tangible than those of climate change.

Your study completion code is GF23.

open_feedback This is our very first study on this topic. If you have any thoughts to share related to our hypothesis, or suggestions for how we could improve this survey, we would be very grateful to hear them.

End of Block: Closing

Study 5: Scientist 2

Start of Block: Consent Form

ConsentForm Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! You must be 18 years or older to participate. We are investigating how people think about current events. In this study, you will be asked to read a news article about a current event, or you will read no article at all. You will then be asked questions about a current event. If you are assigned to an article, the issue you answer questions about may or may not be related, depending on which conditions you get randomly assigned to. The study will take 10 minutes or less. You will receive \$1.75 for your participation. There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]. Should you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, please contact [REDACTED]. Thank you!

Consent Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study.

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and consent to participate (1)
- No I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study. = No I do not consent

End of Block: Consent Form

Start of Block: COVID Condition

ExpLink You have been assigned to read an article about *COVID scientists*.

Covid Article For Experts Who Study Coronaviruses, a Grim Vindication BY CHARLES SCHMIDT 06.08.2020

THE NOW PROPHETIC words could be found buried at the end of a research paper published in the journal *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* in October of 2007: “The presence of a large reservoir of SARS-CoV-like viruses in horseshoe bats, together with the culture of eating exotic animals in southern China, is a time bomb.” The warning – made 13 years ago – came after a wave of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) killed 744 people around the globe. It was among the first to predict the emergence of something like SARS-CoV-2, the virus behind the COVID-19 pandemic. 60% of infectious diseases that have never before reached humans originate in domesticated animals and wildlife. These are often bats, rodents, or non-human primates. Scientists estimate that there are as many as 800,000 zoonotic viruses that could infect humans. “Every future viral threat that people could get already exists and is circulating in those animals — always has been,” said Dennis Carroll, an expert on zoonotic diseases. He is also the former head of the emerging threats division of the United States Agency for International Development, or USAID. Within USAID, Carroll developed a virus catch-and-release project called PREDICT. The program included scientists and researchers from the University of California, Davis and EcoHealth Alliance — all with the goal of discovering new viruses before they spill over into people. Jonna Mazet, the organization’s global director, said that PREDICT collected 168,000 samples from people and animals, and identified more than 900 new viruses. Of those, 160 were coronaviruses — in the same family as SARS-CoV-2. To many experts, the coronavirus pandemic — and the United States’ inability to contain it — has felt like the climate crisis “at warp speed,” says ecologist Jeff Dukes. Both disasters were predicted by scientists and could have been prevented, or at least mitigated, by swift and early action. Climate change is also responsible for the rapid spread of zoonotic diseases, like COVID-19. Events like drought, flooding, and extreme weather force food production to breach habitats populated by virus-carrying wild animals. Although these events are projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at UC Berkeley, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants. Whether or not the pandemic ultimately helps or hinders the prospects for U.S. and global climate action, however, the two crises remain inextricably linked.

COVIDTimer Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: COVID Condition

Start of Block: Climate Change Condition

ControlLink You have been assigned to read an article about *climate change scientists*.

CC Article 40 Years Ago, Scientists Predicted Climate Change BY NEVILLE
NICHOLLS 06.08.2020

THE PROPHETIC WORDS could be found in the conclusion of the Charney Report, created by 10 distinguished climate scientists after a meeting about carbon dioxide and climate change in 1979: “We estimate the most probable warming for a doubling of CO₂ to be near 3°C with a probable error of 1.5°C.” The Report – made over 40 years ago – was the first extensive evaluation of global climate change due to carbon dioxide. The scientists’ forecast of the global temperature rise proved to be incredibly accurate – they had predicted the planet’s warming to within a few hundredths of a degree. Earth-orbiting satellites and other technological advances have enabled scientists to collect data on a global scale. This data reveals the signals of a changing climate. As temperatures increase, the seas rise, droughts and wildfires grow worse, and extreme weather becomes more common. Eventually, entire regions become uninhabitable. “Scientific evidence for warming of the climate system is unequivocal,” said Myles Allen, the head of the Climate Dynamics group at Harvard University, and a scientist for the United States Environmental Protection Agency, or US EPA. Within the US EPA, Allen developed a project called PREDICT. The program included scientists and researchers from Harvard University and Climate Alliance – with the goal of creating climate models to forecast the planet’s temperature increases. Julie Cerqueira, the organization’s global director, said that PREDICT found that carbon dioxide levels today are higher than any point in the last 800,000 years. Temperature trends from around the world support these findings – every one of the past 40 years has been warmer than the 20th century average. To many experts, the coronavirus pandemic — and the United States’ inability to contain it — has felt like the climate crisis “at warp speed,” says ecologist Jeff Dukes. Both disasters were predicted by scientists and could have been prevented, or at least mitigated, by swift and early action. Climate change is also responsible for the rapid spread of zoonotic diseases, like COVID-19. Events like drought, flooding, and extreme weather force food production to breach habitats populated by virus-carrying wild animals. Although these events are projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at UC Berkeley, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants. Whether or not the pandemic ultimately helps or hinders the prospects for U.S. and global climate action, however, the two crises remain inextricably linked.

CCTimer Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Climate Change Condition

Start of Block: Control Condition

Control Overview You have not been assigned to read an article. Please click the arrow to proceed.

End of Block: Control Condition

Start of Block: Attention Check

attentioncheck What is the purpose of the PREDICT project?

- Discovering new viruses before they spill over into people (1)
- Creating climate models to forecast the planet's temperature increases (2)
- Analyzing satellite data to predict the movement of comets (3)
- I did not read an article. (4)

Page Break

End of Block: Attention Check

Start of Block: Covid Belief Q's

Covid-threat How serious of a threat do you think COVID-19 poses as a global health crisis?

- Very serious threat (1)
 - No more serious than the common flu or cold virus (2)
 - Not serious at all (3)
-

face masks From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that wearing a facial mask significantly lowers the risk of COVID-19 transmission?

- Yes, wearing a mask is essential (1)
- Unsure, wearing a mask might help (2)
- No, wearing a mask is unnecessary (3)

End of Block: Covid Belief Q's

Start of Block: Climate Belief Q's

WARMER_T2 From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
 - I'm not sure (3)
 - No, it has not (2)
-

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... != No, it has not

WHY WARMER_T2 Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
- Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
- I'm not sure (6)

End of Block: Climate Belief Q's

Start of Block: Dependent Variables

CC Overview In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

Page Break

p_severity_T2 How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact you?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

c_severity_T2 How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people in general?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

p_vulnerability_T2 How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

c_vulnerability_T2 How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

Page Break

X→

P_per_efficiency_T2 How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

X→

P_res_efficiency_T2 How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

Page Break

C_per_efficiency_T2 How **easy or hard** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

C_res_efficiency_T2 How **effective** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

Page Break

protection_motiv_T2 How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- on climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
 - Moderately unlikely (2)
 - Slightly unlikely (3)
 - Slightly likely (4)
 - Moderately likely (5)
 - Extremely likely (6)
-

pers_behavior How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Eat a largely plant-based diet (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Keep your household energy use as low as possible (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase your use of walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase carbon offsets (donate money for projects that reduce the release of CO2) (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Optimism How likely is it that human beings will effectively respond to climate change?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
- Moderately unlikely (2)
- Slightly unlikely (3)
- Slightly likely (4)
- Moderately likely (5)
- Extremely likely (6)

End of Block: Dependent Variables

Start of Block: Scientist Questions

Climatolog_Role_T2 How much do you agree with the following statements on climatologists?

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat Disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat Agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly Agree (7)
Climatologists should take an active role in public policy debates about scientific issues related to climate change (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists should focus on establishing sound scientific facts and stay out of public policy debates (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists' judgements are based solely on facts (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists act in accordance with public interest (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climatologists are usually better at making good policy decisions about scientific issues related to climate change than	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

other people
(8)

Climatolig.Influ_T2 How much confidence, if any, do you have in climatologists to act in the best interests of the public?

- None at all (1)
 - Not too much (7)
 - A fair amount (8)
 - A great deal (9)
-

Page Break

sci_tech1_T2 How much do you agree with the following statements on science and technology?

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat Disagree (3)	Neither agree nor disagree (4)	Somewhat Agree (5)	Agree (11)	Strongly Agree (12)
Science and technology are making our lives healthier, easier, and more comfortable (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Because of science and technology, there will be more opportunities for the next generation (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

sci_tech2_T2 Consider the following statement about science and technology

	A lot worse off (1)	Worse Off (2)	Somewhat worse off (3)	Neither worse off or better off (4)	Somewhat better off (5)	Better Off (6)	A lot better off (7)
All things considered, would you say the world is better off, or worse off, because of science and technology? (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

sci_tech3_T2 Consider the following statement about science and technology

	Will definitely NOT happen (1)	Will probably NOT happen (2)	Will probably happen (3)	Will definitely happen (4)
New technology will solve most of the problems from global climate change in the next 50 years (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Scientist Questions

Start of Block: Demographics

ethnicity How do you identify? (Check all that apply.)

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
 - Asian (4)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
 - Hispanic (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

gender What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - I identify as (3) _____
-

age What is your year of birth?

education What is the highest level degree or level of education you have completed?

▼ No schooling (1) ... Doctorate (14)

pol_affiliation What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat (1)
 - Independent (2)
 - Republican (3)
 - Other (4) _____
-

pol_leaning Would you describe yourself as relatively more conservative, liberal, or right in the middle?

- Extremely liberal (1)
- Liberal (2)
- Slightly liberal (3)
- Moderate, middle of the road (4)
- Slightly conservative (5)
- Conservative (6)
- Extremely conservative (7)

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Closing

debrief Thank you for your participation in this study! We are exploring how information about scientists' accuracy in predicting issues of public concern (pandemics, climate crises, etc) impacts assessments of risk, and our willingness to take preventive action. Some of you read an article about the accuracy of epidemiologists' predictions. Others of you read an article about the accuracy of climate scientists' predictions. Still others read nothing at all. We hypothesize that reading about scientists' accurate predictions will increase concern about a pressing issue of our time (ie climate change), and therefore lead to people feeling more willing to take action

on behalf of climate change. We think it's possible that reading about epidemiologists' accuracy may be more psychologically impactful, as the effects of COVID-19 are much more immediate and tangible than those of climate change.

Your study completion code is magnus56.

End of Block: Closing

Study 6: Racial Disparity 2

Start of Block: Consent Form

ConsentForm Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! You must be 18 years or older to participate. We are investigating how people think about current events. In this study you will answer some questions about yourself, read a brief news article, and complete several short measures of how you think about the current issue you read about. The study will take 20 minutes or less. You will be compensated the amount you agreed upon before you entered into the survey. The news article you are assigned to read may be about a negative topic. There are no other known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records. If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]. Should you have any questions about your rights as a research participant, please contact the [REDACTED]. Thank you!

consent Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study.

- Yes, I am 18 years or older and consent to participate (1)
- No, I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Block If Please indicate below whether or not you consent to be in this study. = No, I do not consent

Page Break

Start of Block: Demographic Questions

ethnicity How do you identify? (Check all that apply)

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaska Native (3)
 - Asian (4)
 - Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander (5)
 - Hispanic or Latino (6)
 - Other (7) _____
-

gender What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - I identify as (3) _____
-

birth_year What is your age in years?

pol_affiliation What is your political affiliation?

- Democrat (1)
 - Independent (2)
 - Republican (3)
 - Other (4) _____
-

pol_leaning Would you describe yourself as relatively conservative, liberal, or right in the middle?

- Extremely liberal (1)
 - Liberal (2)
 - Slightly liberal (3)
 - Moderate (4)
 - Slightly conservative (5)
 - Conservative (6)
 - Extremely conservative (7)
-

SES What is your wealth class? If you are unsure, you can use ["step one" of the income calculator](#) here:

<https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2020/07/23/are-you-in-the-american-middle-class/>

- Upper income (1)
 - Middle income (2)
 - Lower income (3)
-

Page Break

warmer From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
- I'm not sure (3)
- No, it has not (2)

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the averag... = Yes, it has

Or From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence of climate change that the averag... = I'm not sure

why_warmer Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
- Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
- I'm not sure (6)

Page Break

pollution Have you experienced any of the following effects of pollution? (Check all that apply)

You've lived somewhere where...

- the water isn't safe to drink due to contamination (1)
 - the air isn't safe to breathe due to contamination (2)
 - the food isn't safe to eat due to contamination (3)
 - I have not experienced any of these effects (4)
-

climate_events Have you experienced any of the following climate events? (Check all that apply)

- Heat wave or heat stroke (1)
- Floods (6)
- Sea level rise (7)
- Hurricane (10)
- Wildfires (8)
- Drought (9)
- Animal extinction affecting your livelihood (4)
- Crop failure affecting your livelihood (5)
- I have not experienced any of these effects (11)

End of Block: Demographic Questions

Start of Block: Control Article

control You have been assigned to read an article about *climate change*. Please read the article carefully.

Hurricanes disproportionately harm small coastal communities

Communities on the coast already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from extreme weather disasters

By EMILY PONTECORVO

JUNE 7, 2020 10:59PM (UTC) When Hurricane Florence slammed into southeastern North Carolina in September 2018, the worst-hit communities were on the coast. Not to mention many were still in the process of rebuilding after Hurricane Matthew tore through two years earlier. According to Naeema Muhammad, organizing director of the North Carolina Environmental Justice Network, people in coastal towns like New Bern, Lumberton, and Faison, struggled to evacuate. "People are pretty much left on their own to try to navigate out of danger," Muhammad told Grist. When the flooding came, it flushed coal ash, animal waste, and human waste from wastewater treatment plants into the waterways, which spilled over riverbanks and into the streets. "People had to navigate through that water," she said. If you had been following coverage of the hurricane on one of the major nightly news shows at the time, you might have missed this story entirely. That's because not a single segment that aired on ABC's World News Tonight, the CBS Evening News, or the NBC Nightly News reported on the disparate impacts Florence had on smaller coastal communities, instead focusing on the impacts of the hurricane on larger cities affected, like Greenville, North Carolina. The media watchdog nonprofit analyzed 669 segments produced by those shows from 2017 to 2019 covering seven hurricanes, including Florence, and one tropical storm. Not one addressed the fact that these extreme weather events did not affect everyone in their paths equally — that the devastation they brought smaller coastal areas was far worse — despite ample research highlighting this disparity. "It does not come as a surprise at all," Muhammad said of the study. "We have a lot of issues going on in the floodplain areas that do not get addressed by the media." Small coastal communities already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from the extreme weather that becomes more common with climate change, especially hurricanes, flooding, and rising sea levels, because they tend to have less infrastructure than large cities. As the Media Matters report states, "These events expose vulnerabilities, but they often go unexplained — partly because broadcast TV news fails to even do the minimum of reporting on who is being harmed the most." Although extreme weather is projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at Berkeley University, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants.

control_time Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

Q71 The article I read was about...

- The Ridgecrest Earthquakes (0)
- The Chico Wildfires (0)
- Hurricane Florence (1)
- New Mexico's Drought (0)
- I did not read an article (0)

Display This Question:

If The article I read was about... = Hurricane Florence

Q72 The article I read said Hurricane Florence strongly impacted

- The fishing industry (0)
- Communities of color (2)
- Cruise ship routes (0)
- Small coastal towns (1)
- Beachside resorts (0)

End of Block: Control Article

Start of Block: Experimental Article

experimental You have been assigned to read an article about climate change. Please read the article carefully.

Hurricanes disproportionately harm communities of color
Communities of color already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from extreme

weather disasters

By EMILY PONTECORVO

JUNE 7, 2020 10:59PM (UTC)

When Hurricane Florence slammed into southeastern North Carolina in September 2018, the worst-hit communities were already dealing with a litany of hazards: poverty, pollution from coal ash ponds and lagoons filled with livestock waste, and chemicals in the drinking water. Not to mention many were still in the process of rebuilding after Hurricane Matthew tore through two years earlier. According to Naeema Muhammad, organizing director of the North Carolina Environmental Justice Network, people in these largely black and brown communities in cities like New Bern and Lumberton, and rural towns like Faison, struggled to evacuate. "People are pretty much left on their own to try to navigate out of danger," Muhammad told Grist. When the flooding came, it flushed coal ash, animal waste, and human waste from wastewater treatment plants into the waterways, which spilled over riverbanks and into the streets. "People had to navigate through that water," she said. If you had been following coverage of the hurricane on one of the major nightly news shows at the time, you might have missed this story entirely. That's because not a single segment that aired on ABC's World News Tonight, the CBS Evening News, or the NBC Nightly News reported on the disparate impacts Florence had on marginalized communities, according to a new analysis by Media Matters. The media watchdog nonprofit analyzed 669 segments produced by those shows from 2017 to 2019 covering seven hurricanes, including Florence, and one tropical storm. Not one addressed the fact that these extreme weather events did not affect everyone in their paths equally — that the devastation they brought to poor communities and communities of color was far worse — despite ample research highlighting this disparity. "It does not come as a surprise at all," Muhammad said of the study. "We have a lot of issues going on in the floodplain areas that do not get addressed by the media. It's mainly because of the faces in those areas," which are predominantly Black, Native American, and Latino. Marginalized communities already have and will continue to suffer disproportionately from the extreme weather that becomes more common with climate change, from hurricanes and flooding to heat waves and wildfires. This is not just because they are more likely to live in the floodplain or the line of fire, although that is part of it, and is often the result of racist practices like redlining. Low-income and minority communities are also more likely to live in poor-quality housing and to not have the means to evacuate, rebuild, or relocate. As the Media Matters report states, "These events expose vulnerabilities stemming from historic and systemic inequities, but they too often go unexplained — partly because broadcast TV news fails to even do the minimum of reporting on who is being harmed the most." Although extreme weather is projected to increase as climate change worsens, it is not too late to begin curbing the effects of climate change. According to a recent study conducted by researchers at Berkeley University, the United States can achieve 90% clean, carbon-free electricity nationwide by 2035. Because the price of renewable energy is plummeting, this can be achieved at no extra cost to consumers, and without new fossil fuel plants.

experimental_time Timing

First Click (1)

Last Click (2)

Page Submit (3)

Click Count (4)

Page Break

Q69 The article I read was about...

- The Ridgecrest Earthquakes (0)
- The Chico Wildfires (0)
- Hurricane Florence (1)
- New Mexico's Drought (0)
- I did not read an article (0)

Display This Question:

If The article I read was about... = Hurricane Florence

Q70 The article I read said Hurricane Florence strongly impacted

- The fishing industry (0)
- Communities of color (2)
- Cruise ship routes (0)
- Small coastal towns (1)
- Beachside resorts (0)

End of Block: Experimental Article

Start of Block: Questions about article

affective_measures Think about the article you read earlier. The article made me feel...

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat Disagree (3)	Somewhat Agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly Agree (7)
Angry (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Guilty (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Overwhelmed (10)	<input type="radio"/>					
Indifferent (11)	<input type="radio"/>					
Afraid (12)	<input type="radio"/>					
Surprised (13)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hopeful (14)	<input type="radio"/>					
Calm (16)	<input type="radio"/>					
Motivated (18)	<input type="radio"/>					

End of Block: Questions about article

Start of Block: Enviro Questions

Q138 In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

vul_p How likely is it that the effects of climate change will impact you?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (4)
 - High chance (5)
 - Very high chance (6)
-

vul_c How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people in general?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (4)
 - High chance (5)
 - Very high chance (6)
-

vul_personal What is the likelihood of encountering the following events in your lifetime?

	No chance at all (1)	Very low chance (2)	Low chance (3)	Moderate chance (5)	High chance (7)	Very high chance (8)
Sea level rise (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hurricanes (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Wildfires (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Droughts (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Extreme heat waves (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

vul_collective What is the likelihood of encountering the following events for people in general?

	No chance at all (1)	Very low chance (2)	Low chance (3)	Moderate chance (5)	High chance (7)	Very high chance (8)
Sea level rise (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Hurricanes (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Wildfires (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Droughts (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Extreme heat waves (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

severity_p How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

severity_c How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

PE_p How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

PE_c How **easy or hard** would it be for people in general to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_p How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_c How **effective** would it be for people in general to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

Page Break

Q46 In this section, we would like you to think about people who share the same ethnic identity you most strongly identify with.

vul_e How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people who share your ethnic identity?

- No chance (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

severity_e How much negative impact will climate change have on people who share your ethnic identity?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

PE_e How **easy or hard** would it be for people who share your ethnic identity to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

RE_e How **effective** would it be for people who share your ethnic identity to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
 - I don't believe in climate change (7)
-

Page Break

behavioral_motive How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- on climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
- Moderately unlikely (2)
- Slightly unlikely (3)
- Slightly likely (4)
- Moderately likely (5)
- Extremely likely (6)

Page Break

X→

behavioral_intent How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Minimize meat consumption (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support eco-friendly brands and businesses (11)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Conserve household energy use (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Choose walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Join an organization that fights climate change (12)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Recycle
and/or
compost (10)

Support an
organization
that combats
environmental
racism (13)

Read or
watch news
related to
climate
change (14)

maladaptive_behavior How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Turn off the TV when it mentions climate disasters (hurricanes, wildfires, etc) (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Throw something recyclable in the trash to save time (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Avoid reading news articles with climate change in the title (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Drive somewhere within walking distance to save time (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

End of Block: Enviro Questions

Start of Block: Self Affirmation task

self_affirmation Please take a moment to identify a value that is important to you. Briefly summarize this value below, and write a sentence or two about why this value is important to you. Describe a time when you expressed this value in your life.

Page Break

Q73 Thank you for completing our survey! We are interested in how learning about racial disparities in the effects of climate change impact people's concern and willingness to take action. Some of you read an article about climate change heavily impacting coastal towns (the control condition), and others read an article about climate change heavily impacting communities of color (the experimental condition). We will evaluate whether the articles lead to different levels of concern and willingness to act.

Your completion code is benj8

End of Block: Self Affirmation task

Study 7: Prospection 2

Start of Block: Consent

Q1 Welcome!

Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! This survey is part of a larger research project conducted at Oberlin College. In this study, you will answer some questions about yourself and your views, and respond to several short writing prompts. This study will take approximately 10 minutes. To thank you for your time, you will be paid \$2.00. You must be 18 years or older to participate in this research.

There are no known risks associated with your participation in this research study. The answers and information you provide in this study will remain confidential. Should the data be published, no individual information will be disclosed. Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to answer any particular question you do not wish to answer for any reason, and you are free to discontinue participation completely at any point for any reason and still receive payment. We encourage you to print this consent form for your records.

If you have any additional questions about the study, please contact [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]. For questions concerning the rights of human subjects, please

contact [REDACTED]

- I am 18 years or older (1)
- I am not 18 years or older (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Welcome! Thank you for your interest in participating in our study! This survey is part of a lar... = I am not 18 years or older

consent By checking below, you acknowledge that you have read the above information and give your consent to participate.

- I consent to participate (1)
- I do not consent (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If By checking below, you acknowledge that you have read the above information and give your consent... = I do not consent

Page Break

Mood_PreManip People's moods change all the time. How are you feeling right now?

I don't feel this way I very much feel this way

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

End of Block: Consent

Start of Block: Positive condition image - solar

Pos1_Picture

As greenhouse gas emissions continue, scientists predict temperature rises of 2.5 to 10 degrees Fahrenheit within the next century. The extent of climate change's damage to people's livelihoods and ecosystems will depend on the resilience and adaptive ability of the social and environmental systems in place in each area. Already, communities around the country are working to find ways to increase their resilience to extreme weather conditions and become more sustainable.

Solar installation in Littlestown, PA:

End of Block: Mood2

Start of Block: Negative condition - drought

Neg2_Picture As average global temperatures rise and weather patterns become more variable, agriculture faces new challenges. Climate change accelerates soil degradation and decreases crop yields, and different areas become more susceptible to either intense droughts or flooding. As a result of these difficulties, new approaches to agriculture are being developed. These approaches include special practices like crop diversification and reducing tillage and water use, while also including a growing support of local farms and community gardens.

Texas farmer during drought:

Neg2_Q1 Imagine you are living in this future:
 How would you feel? What would you see, hear, smell?
 Describe what your life would be like.

Neg2_Q2 Would you want to live in a future that looked like the image shown above? Why?

Q94 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Negative condition - drought

Start of Block: Combined positive and negative

Both1_PosNeg_PosPic

As greenhouse gas emissions continue, scientists predict temperature rises of 2.5 to 10 degrees Fahrenheit within the next century. The extent of climate change's damage to people's livelihoods and ecosystems will depend on the resilience and adaptive ability of the social and environmental systems in place in each area. Already, communities around the country are working to find ways to increase their resilience to extreme weather conditions and become more sustainable.

Solar installation in Littlestown, PA:

Both1_PosNeg_Q1 Imagine you are living in this future:
How would you feel? What would you see, hear, smell?
Describe what your life would be like.

Both1_PosNeg_Q2 Would you want to live in a future that looked like the image shown above?
Why?

Both1_PosNeg_NegPic As average global temperatures rise and weather patterns become more variable, agriculture faces new challenges. Climate change accelerates soil degradation and decreases crop yields, and different areas become more susceptible to either intense droughts or flooding. As a result of these difficulties, new approaches to agriculture are being developed. These approaches include special practices like crop diversification and reducing tillage and water use, while also including a growing support of local farms and community gardens.

Texas farmer during drought:

Both1_PosNeg_Q3 Imagine you are living in this future:
How would you feel? What would you see, hear, smell?
Describe what your life would be like.

Both1_PosNeg_Q4 Would you want to live in a future that looked like the image shown above?
Why?

Q97 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Combined positive and negative

Start of Block: Combined negative and positive

Both1_NegPos_NegPic As average global temperatures rise and weather patterns become more variable, agriculture faces new challenges. Climate change accelerates soil degradation and decreases crop yields, and different areas become more susceptible to either intense droughts or flooding. As a result of these difficulties, new approaches to agriculture are being

developed. These approaches include special practices like crop diversification and reducing tillage and water use, while also including a growing support of local farms and community gardens.

Texas farmer during drought:

Both1_NegPos_Q1 Imagine you are living in this future:
How would you feel? What would you see, hear, smell?
Describe what your life would be like.

Both1_NegPos_Q2 Would you want to live in a future that looked like the image shown above?
Why?

Both1_NegPos_PosPic

As greenhouse gas emissions continue, scientists predict temperature rises of 2.5 to 10 degrees Fahrenheit within the next century. The extent of climate change's damage to people's

livelihoods and ecosystems will depend on the resilience and adaptive ability of the social and environmental systems in place in each area. Already, communities around the country are working to find ways to increase their resilience to extreme weather conditions and become more sustainable.

Solar installation in Littlestown, PA:

Both1_NegPos_Q3 Imagine you are living in this future:
How would you feel? What would you see, hear, smell?
Describe what your life would be like.

Both1_NegPos_Q4 Would you want to live in a future that looked like the image shown above?
Why?

Q96 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: Combined negative and positive

Start of Block: Control

placeholder Please continue to the next question.

End of Block: Control

Start of Block: ECAS

ECAS_T2 Rate your agreement with each of the following statements, based on how you feel right now.

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Somewhat Disagree (3)	Neither Agree nor Disagree (4)	Somewhat Agree (5)	Agree (6)	Strongly Agree (7)
I can easily imagine a world in which we supply all of our energy needs without harming the natural world. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to imagine a world where we no longer use fossil fuels. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can clearly imagine a world where we exclusively use agricultural practices that protect the natural habitats of animals. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I can imagine a world where politicians care more about minimizing the population's negative impact on the environment than economic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

growth. (4)

I can think of numerous methods of achieving a world where carbon emissions are reduced below current levels. (5)

I can easily imagine a system in which the government reflects the interests of the natural environment rather than the interests of the wealthy. (6)

I can easily imagine a world where people see themselves as integrated with nature, rather than masters over the natural world. (7)

When I imagine what an ecologically sustainable existence for humans would be like, I can picture it in detail. (8)

A harmonious relationship

between humans and the natural world is easy for me to imagine. (9)

I have a clear understanding of all the ways that a sustainable human existence would differ from our current state of affairs. (10)

End of Block: ECAS

Start of Block: All Conditions CC & Demographic Questions

CC_Q's In the next section, you will be answering questions about *climate change*. Climate change, also known as global warming, is the change in global or regional climate patterns due to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

WARMER_T2 From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on earth has been getting warmer over the past few decades, or not?

- Yes, it has (1)
 - I'm not sure (3)
 - No, it has not (2)
-

Display This Question:

If From what you've read and heard before, is there solid evidence that the average temperature on e... = Yes, it has

WHY_WARMER_T2 Do you believe that the earth is getting warmer (a) mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels or (b) mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment?

- Mostly because of human activity such as burning fossil fuels (1)
 - Mostly because of natural patterns in the earth's environment (2)
 - I'm not sure (6)
-

impact_ind_T2 How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact you?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

severity_ind_T2 How much negative impact will climate change have on you?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Between small and moderate impact (4)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Between moderate and large impact (6)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

impact_collect_T2 How likely is it that the effects of climate change impact people in general?

- No chance at all (1)
 - Very low chance (2)
 - Low chance (3)
 - Moderate chance (5)
 - High chance (7)
 - Very high chance (8)
-

severity_collect_T2 How much negative impact will climate change have on people in general?

- No impact at all (1)
 - Very small impact (2)
 - Small impact (3)
 - Between small and moderate impact (4)
 - Moderate impact (5)
 - Between moderate and large impact (6)
 - Large impact (7)
 - Very large impact (8)
-

perf_eff_ind_T2 How **easy or hard** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

resp_eff_ind_T2 How **effective** would it be for you personally to address climate change through your actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

perf_eff_collect_T2 How **easy or hard** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely hard (1)
 - Moderately hard (2)
 - Slightly hard (3)
 - Slightly easy (4)
 - Moderately easy (5)
 - Extremely easy (6)
-

resp_eff_collect_T2 How **effective** would it be for people in the United States to address climate change through their actions?

- Extremely ineffective (1)
 - Moderately ineffective (2)
 - Slightly ineffective (3)
 - Slightly effective (4)
 - Moderately effective (5)
 - Extremely effective (6)
-

protect_motiv_T2 How likely is it that you will take action -- big or small -- to fight climate change within the next six months?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
 - Moderately unlikely (2)
 - Slightly unlikely (3)
 - Slightly likely (4)
 - Moderately likely (5)
 - Extremely likely (6)
-

CC_Humanity_T2 How likely is it that human beings will effectively respond to climate change?

- Extremely unlikely (1)
 - Moderately unlikely (2)
 - Slightly unlikely (3)
 - Slightly likely (4)
 - Moderately likely (5)
 - Extremely likely (6)
-

CC_Temporal_T2 When do you expect climate change to affect the following?

	Climate change won't affect this (1)	Not very soon, in several decades (2)	About a decade from now (3)	Soon, within a year or two (4)	It's already being affected (5)
The weather in my neighborhood (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The source of my electricity (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wildlife and landscapes in my area (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My relative wealth (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The weather globally (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others' relative wealth (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Zoonotic disease (disease spread by animals) (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase in Heat Waves (8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sea Levels (9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Ocean Acidification (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Beh_Int_T2 How likely is it that in the next six months you will...

	Extremely unlikely (1)	Moderately unlikely (2)	Slightly unlikely (3)	Slightly likely (4)	Moderately likely (5)	Extremely likely (6)
Reduce your household energy use (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vote for candidates committed to reducing or stopping climate change (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase your use of walking, biking, and/or public transportation (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Call or write an elected official about climate change (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Donate money to an organization that fights climate change (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Purchase carbon offsets (donate money for projects that reduce the release of CO2) (10)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Get around without a car (e.g. walk, bike, bus, carpool)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

when possible (11)

Talk about climate change with others (12)

Ethnicity_T2 How do you identify? (Check all that apply).

- White (1)
 - Black or African American (2)
 - American Indian or Alaskan Native (3)
 - Hispanic or Latino (4)
 - Asian (5)
 - Middle Eastern/North African (6)
 - Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander (7)
 - Other (please specify) (8)
-

Gender_T2 What is your gender?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- I identify as (3) _____

Pol_Aff_T2 Generally speaking, do you usually think of yourself as a Republican, a Democrat, an Independent, or something else?

- Republican (1)
- Democrat (2)
- Independent (3)
- Other (4)

Pol_Leaning_T2 Here is a 7-point scale on which the political views that people might hold are arranged from extremely liberal (left) to extremely conservative (right). Where would you place yourself on this scale?

Extremely Liberal (0)	Extremely Liberal (0)	Liberal (1)	Slightly Liberal (2)	Neutral (3)	Slightly Conservative (4)	Conservative (5)	Extremely Conservative (6)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>					

End of Block: All Conditions CC & Demographic Questions

Start of Block: Completion Code

Q92 Your completion code is GR23APE

End of Block: Completion Code
